

“RBP-ReguNet”

Deliverable 6.1

RBP-ReguNet public Web 2.0 platforms

PROJECT INFORMATION

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER	101073094
PROJECT FULL TITLE	RBP-ReguNET – Deconstructing and Rewiring RNA-RBP regulatory networks
PROJECT ACRONYM	RBP-ReguNet
FUNDING SCHEME	HORIZON EUROPE
START DATE OF THE PROJECT	1/3/2022
DURATION (MONTHS)	48
CALL IDENTIFIER	HORIZON-MSCA-DN-2021
PROJECT WEBSITE	www.rbp-regunet.eu

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

DELIVERABLE N°	6.1
DELIVERABLE NAME	RBP-ReguNet public Web 2.0 platforms
WP NAME	WP6. Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach Activities
WP LEADER	USC
CONTRIBUTING PARTNERS	ALL
NATURE	DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc
AUTHORS	Ashwin Woodhoo
REVIEWERS	Adrián Posado Fernández
DEADLINE (PROJECT MONTH)	2
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PUBLIC

DOCUMENT LOG

NUMBER	DATE	AUTHOR	DESCRIPTION OF CHANGE
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2	21/8/2023	Adrián Posado Fernández	Content Addition
3	23/8/2023	Adrián Posado Fernández	Content Addition
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1. GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

DC	Doctoral Candidate
DN	Doctoral Network
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
PI	Principal Investigator
RBP	RNA-Binding Proteins

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable introduces the website and social network profiles established for the MSCA-DN RBP-ReguNet research project. These digital assets are set to become accessible starting from the sixth month of the project's timeline, playing a pivotal role in facilitating our dissemination and exploitation endeavours.

The website, developed using the WordPress platform, serves as a comprehensive repository of essential project-related details. It concisely outlines the project's overarching objectives, the consortium's composition, and introduces the cohort of Doctoral Candidates (DCs) involved, among other pertinent information. Moreover, the website serves as the main open access point, supporting part of the Open Science Framework that will be established (Deliverable 6.3), and providing contact information that can be utilized by external stakeholders keen on engaging with the project.

The social media profiles are aimed to reach a bigger audience, feeding the website and increasing exposure of any development, event, or publication from the project.

This report explains why and how we made the website and social media profiles for the RBP-ReguNet project, how we intend to use them, and the benefits they bring to the project.

3. PROJECT'S WEBSITE

The RBP-ReguNet project's website (www.rbp-regunet.eu) has been designed to provide resources and information to various audiences, including general public, students, scientific communities, as well as project partners.

A website is a powerful tool to enhance the visibility and outreach of the project. By providing a dedicated online presence, the project gains a platform to showcase its objectives, progress, and outcomes. This easily accessible hub becomes a central point of reference for interested parties, ranging from fellow researchers and academia to industry professionals and the general public. Through well-organized content, the website effectively communicates the project's significance, goals, and the innovative solutions it offers. It offers an opportunity to highlight the contributions of the research team, including DCs, fostering a sense of community and collaboration.

The website's interactive features, such as news updates, blog posts, and multimedia content, engage visitors and keep them informed about the project's latest developments. This dynamic interaction cultivates interest and encourages continuous engagement. Moreover, the website facilitates effective communication with stakeholders beyond the immediate research circle. Contact information, social media integration, and downloadable resources enable interested parties to connect, collaborate, and share project insights across diverse networks such as Twitter (X), Instagram, and LinkedIn.

In summary, the website amplifies the project's visibility by offering an informative, interactive, and accessible platform to all audiences. It extends the project's reach, strengthens its impact, and fosters meaningful connections within the research community and beyond.

The website has been already developed and ready to be released in month 6 of the project. Technically, it has been implemented using the WordPress, featuring a custom-designed theme and several sections dedicated to the main project's stakeholders.

3.1. Technical basis

The website was developed using WordPress (<https://wordpress.org>), Elementor (<https://elementor.com>) and several additional plug-ins (<https://wordpress.org/plugins/>). It is dynamic, responsive, and adaptable to all available desktop, laptop and mobile devices.

3.2. Structure

The structure of the website was developed considering every stakeholder involved in the project: institutions, investigators, DCs, and the EU; as well as the funding programme Horizon Europe - Marie-Sklodowska Curie Actions. The sections are structured following the scheme in Table 1.

Table 1. Website Structure.

Home	General Information
About us	Coordinator Beneficiaries Associated Partners External Advisors
The Network	Academic & Scientific Objectives Work Packages Principal Investigators (PIs) Doctoral Candidates (DCs)
Achievements	Milestones & Achievements Public Deliverables
Newsroom	Blog and Social Media Posts
The Programme	Marie Skłodowska Curie Horizon Europe MSCA-DN Any Doubts?
Contact	E-mail and Social Media Profiles

3.3. Appearance

The website utilizes a colour palette and theme (background images, font) based on the logo developed for the project (Table 2).

Table 2. Website's fonts and colour palette.

Logo Font	Liberation Serif
Website Font	For Heading Menu: Arial For Content: CordialUPC Bold
Colour Palette	#AEC779 #6C8C47 #92BD60 #B767B3 #DEB8DC #D4E1C5 #CBDFB3

3.4. Content

The website holds essential and pertinent details concerning the RBP-ReguNet project. This encompasses an abstract, a roster of participating partners (both beneficiaries and associated partners), project objectives, the organizational framework of work packages aligned with specific goals, the individuals engaged in the project (comprising Principal Investigators and Doctoral Candidates), as well as a brief portrayal of the historical figure Marie-Sklodowska Curie, alongside explanations of the funding initiatives Horizon Europe and

MSCA-DN. Additionally, we have incorporated essential contact information for reaching out to the project coordinator.

The website also has three interactive sections designed to actively engage the public. The first section is titled "Milestones and Achievements," where we display noteworthy milestones, posters, and other scientific communications. These are presented as downloadable PDFs and encompass pertinent non-IPR-related outcomes and discoveries. The purpose is to facilitate and promote transparent communication following the principles of the Open Science Framework (as outlined in Deliverable 6.3), which will be established within the consortium.

The second section is labelled "Deliverables," and it serves as a platform to share compelling deliverables from the project that are accessible to the public. These materials will be available as downloadable PDFs.

Lastly, the third section operates as a dynamic "newsroom," dedicated to sharing concise posts about project-related news, events, and significant highlights.

3.5. Samples/Screenshots

Home Section

The screenshot shows the home page of the RBP-ReguNet website. At the top left is the RBP-ReguNet logo. A navigation menu includes 'Home', 'About us', 'The Network', 'Achievements', 'Newsroom', 'The Programme', and 'Contact'. The main banner features a world map background with a large illustration of a brain and RNA-protein interactions. The headline reads 'Deconstructing and Rewiring RNA-RBP regulatory networks: RBP-ReguNet'. Below this, a sub-headline states: 'RBP-ReguNet unlocks the secrets of RNA-binding proteins, paving the way for groundbreaking therapies and future scientific leaders.' A 'The Network' button is positioned below the sub-headline. Two columns of text describe the project's goals and the training it offers. A row of partner logos follows, including Università di Trento, Sanquin, Gaertor, SCITEC, Ribonexus, and UPF. An 'About Us' button is centered below the logos. At the bottom of the page, there is a 'Contact us' section with the RBP-ReguNet logo and a 'Contact us' link. A European Union funding notice is also present, stating: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101073094'.

**Funded by
the European Union**

About us Section

RBP-ReguNet Home About us The Network Achievements Newsroom The Programme Contact

RBP-ReguNet nucleates seven leading academic experts and one industrial partner from five European countries. Five more Academic, plus two non-Academic Associated Partners will support research and academic activities, bringing expertise in key areas.

Coordinator

USC
 Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (Spain)

Beneficiaries

Sanquin
 Stichting Sanquin Biovoorziening (The Netherlands)

UNITN – Università degli Studi di Trento (Italy)

UMIL – Università degli Studi di Milano (Italy)

EMBL – European Molecular Biology Laboratory (Germany)

IMMAGINA Biotechnology (Italy)

IC – Institut Curie (France)

CRG – Fundacio Centre de Regulacio Genomica (Spain)

Associated Partners

UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM
 UVA – Universiteit van Amsterdam (The Netherlands)

MRC-CVR – University of Glasgow (United Kingdom)

université PARIS-SACLAY
 UPSaclay – Université Paris-Saclay (France)

upf. Universitat Pompeu Fabra Barcelona
 UPF – Universitat Pompeu Fabra (Spain)

Ribonexus (France)

CNR – Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italy)

Kaertor Foundation (Spain)

Contact us

RBP-ReguNet
 Deconstructing and Rewiring RNA-RBP regulatory networks: RBP-ReguNet

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101073094

The Network Section

RBP-ReguNet Home About us **The Network** Achievements Newsroom The Programme Contact

Academic & Scientific objectives Work Packages Principal Investigators (PIs) Doctoral Candidates (DCs)

We have established RBP-ReguNet to take advantage of this new window of opportunity to identify druggable targets for a range of untreatable diseases, including cancer, neurological, liver, immune and infectious diseases.

We will train 11 DCs in a range of core research skills, state-of-the-art discipline-specific skills that will span from computational, structural, molecular and cellular biology to medicinal chemistry and pharmacological screening, transferable skills, and entrepreneurial skills by hosting or secondments to non-academic partners, and through a range of network-wide training activities.

We will provide them with an international, inter-sectoral and interdisciplinary research program in line with the 3I's principle of the EU Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training.

Preclinical Models

Discovery - Interactome Mapping

Molecular Function

Computational Biology

Drug Discovery - HTS

Structural Biology

Proof-of-concept therapy

Business Entrepreneurship

PhD Awarding Universities

RBP-ReguNet

The Network

Academic & Scientific objectives **Work Packages** **Principal Investigators (PIs)** **Doctoral Candidates (DCs)**

Wp N°	WP title	Lead Beneficiary	DC involvement
WP1	To identify candidate RBPs from pathological models	EMBL	1,2
WP2	To uncover biological function of candidate RBPs	IC, CRG	1-7, 9
WP3	To characterize the molecular mechanisms of action of candidate RBPs	IMMAGINA	1-8
WP4	Therapeutic targeting of RBPs	UMIL	9, 10, 11
WP5	Scientific training and transferable training	CRG	All
WP6	Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach Activities	USC	All
WP7	Network Management	USC	All

Academic & Scientific objectives **Work Packages** **Principal Investigators (PIs)** **Doctoral Candidates (DCs)**

Prof. Ashwin Woodhoo
Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (Spain)
Coordinator

Dr. María Varela Rey
Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (Spain)
Principal Investigator

Dr. Adrián Posado Fernández
Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (Spain)
Project Manager

Prof. Stechan Vagner
Institut Curie (France)
Principal Investigator

Prof. Fátima Gebauer
Fundacio Centre de Regulacio Genomica (Spain)
Principal Investigator

Prof. Juan Valcárcel
Fundacio Centre de Regulacio Genomica (Spain)
Principal Investigator

Prof. Monika Wolkers
Stichting Sanquin Bloedvoorziening (The Netherlands)
Principal Investigator

Dr. Massimiliano Clamer
Biotechnology (Italy)
Principal Investigator

Prof. Alessandro Provenazi
Università degli Studi di Trento (Italy)
Principal Investigator

Prof. Pierfausto Seneci
Università degli Studi di Milano (Italy)
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Prof. Mathias Hentze
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Principal Investigator

Prof. Alfredo Castello
University of Glasgow (United Kingdom)
Principal Investigator

Prof. Mabel Loza
Kaetor Foundation (Spain)

Matthieu Coutet
Ribonexus (France)

Dr. Daniela Arosio
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italy)
Principal Investigator

Academic & Scientific objectives **Work Packages** **Principal Investigators (PIs)** **Doctoral Candidates (DCs)**

DC1

WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6, WP7

DC2

DC3

*under construction

Achievements Section

The screenshot shows the 'Achievements' section of the RBP-ReguNet website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'Home', 'About us', 'The Network', 'Achievements', 'Newsroom', 'The Programme', and 'Contact'. The main heading is 'Achievements', with sub-sections for 'Milestones and Achievements' and 'Public Deliverables'. Below this, there is a 'Contact us' link. The RBP-ReguNet logo is displayed, along with the tagline 'Deconstructing and Rewiring RNA-RBP regulatory networks: RBP-ReguNet'. A European Union flag is shown with the text: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101073094'. At the bottom, there is a 'Funded by the European Union' logo.

Newsroom Section

The screenshot shows the 'Newsroom' section of the RBP-ReguNet website. The navigation menu is similar to the Achievements section, but 'Newsroom' is highlighted. The main heading is 'Newsroom'. Below this, there is a date 'June 16, 2023' and a circular diagram showing the RBP-ReguNet network structure. The diagram includes various scientific fields and institutions. Below the diagram, there is a text block: 'The RBP-ReguNet is born: A European consortium that seeks new drugs for untreated diseases such as certain types of cancer, neurological disorders, or hepatic and infectious conditions.'

The Programme Section

[Marie Skłodowska Curie](#)
[Horizon Europe](#)
[MSCA-DN](#)
[Any Doubts?](#)

Who was Marie Skłodowska Curie?

Marie Curie was the first truly famous woman scientist in the modern world. She was known as the "Mother of Modern Physics" for her pioneer work in research about radioactivity, a word she coined. She was the first woman awarded a Ph.D. in research science in Europe and the first woman professor at the Sorbonne¹. Curie discovered and isolated polonium and radium, and established the nature of radiation and beta rays¹.

In 1903, Marie Curie became the first woman to win a Nobel Prize, sharing it with her husband Pierre Curie and Henri Becquerel for their work on radioactivity². She won another Nobel Prize in 1911 for her discovery of radium and polonium³.

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) is an EU funding programme that supports doctoral and postdoctoral researchers in Europe. It is named after Marie Curie because of her pioneering work in radioactivity and her role as a woman in science⁵.

1. Marie Curie – Mother of Modern Physics – ThoughtCo
2. Marie Curie | Biography, Nobel Prize, Accomplishments, & Facts
3. Why is Marie Curie known as the mother of modern physics?
4. Marie Curie: Mother of Modern Physics – Google Books
5. Who was Marie Curie and why did she give her name to a European research program?

[Marie Skłodowska Curie](#)
[Horizon Europe](#)
[MSCA-DN](#)
[Any Doubts?](#)

Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation. It tackles climate change, helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth.

The MSCA programme is located within the Pillar 1 of Horizon Europe.

Horizon Europe is organized in Six Clusters (Health, Culture, Creativity & Inclusive Societies, Civil Security for Society, Digital, Industry & Space, Climate, Energy & Mobility, and Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment), covering Five Mission Areas

Five Mission Areas

[Marie Skłodowska Curie](#)
[Horizon Europe](#)
[MSCA-DN](#)
[Any Doubts?](#)

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions for Doctoral candidates

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions fund excellent research and innovation and equip researchers at all stages of their career with new knowledge and skills, through mobility across borders and exposure to different sectors and disciplines. The MSCA help build Europe's capacity for research and innovation by investing in the long-term careers of excellent researchers.

The MSCA also fund the development of excellent doctoral and postdoctoral training programmes and collaborative research projects worldwide. By doing so, they achieve a structuring impact on higher education institutions, research centres and non-academic organisations.

The MSCA promote excellence and set standards for high-quality researcher education and training in line with the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the recruitment of researchers.

Objective of Doctoral Networks

The objective of Doctoral Networks is to implement doctoral programmes

🔗 [Embark on a career in research](#)

duration of each fellowship is between 3 and 36 months (between 3 and 48 months in the case of Joint Doctorate fellowships).

[Marie Skłodowska Curie](#)
[Horizon Europe](#)
[MSCA-DN](#)
[Any Doubts?](#)

Any doubts?

Feel free to contact the Project Manager in case you have any questions about the organization of the project.

In any case, the [network of National Contact Points \(NCPs\)](#) is the main structure to provide guidance, practical information and assistance on all aspects of participation in Horizon Europe. NCPs are also established in many non-EU and non-associated countries ("third countries").

[Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions](#)

[Funding & Tender Opportunities](#)

Contact Section

The screenshot shows the 'Contact' section of the RBP-ReguNet website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the RBP-ReguNet logo and menu items: Home, About us, The Network, Achievements, Newsroom, The Programme, and Contact. Below the navigation bar is a large green banner with the word 'Contact' in white. Underneath the banner is a light green section with the RBP-ReguNet logo and the text 'Contact us'. Below this, there is a small European Union flag and the text: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101073094'. At the bottom of the page, there is a larger European Union flag and the text 'Funded by the European Union'.

*under construction

4. SOCIAL MEDIA

To diversify and maximize the target audiences we have created social media profiles at the professional network **LinkedIn**, and in the more general networks **Twitter** and **Instagram**. We intend to use the profiles at these social networks to increase visibility of project's main achievements in general, non-scientific communities, communicating them in a simple, comprehensive, and attractive manner.

The profiles will also serve as channels to feed new visits to the website, maximising the outreach and exposure.

Instagram and **Twitter (X)**: @RBP-ReguNet

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/mscadn-rbp-regunet-95a952261>

5. CONCLUSION

With the development and launch of the website and the social network profiles we aim to significantly increase the visibility and outreach of the objectives, involved people and institutions, and results of the RBP-ReguNet project.

6. DEVIATIONS

The present deliverable was submitted on month 6 instead of on month 2 of the project due to the delayed incorporation of the project's main project manager to the staff team, along with the fact that DCs will not be incorporated until month 7. This pushed the website construction to month 6 and the expected release with complete information to month 7, when most of the DCs will incorporate the project.

We do not expect this delay to impact the submission of other deliverables nor the progress of the DC's individual projects.